

Exploring Effective Leadership Models within Private Higher Education Institutions in England

Sarwar Khawaja

Oxford Business College (OBC), Oxford, UK

Abstract

Leadership is the main ingredient for the success of organisations. Its context has been melded in Private Higher Education Institutions (PHEIs) by the shifts in technological modes of teaching and learning and its response to the demand of the new generation and competition. The purpose of this empirical study is to identify leadership practices and their effectiveness that will help PHEIs achieve institutional goals and vision, manage their operations, maintain good relationships, and lead with a high-quality education. The overarching question is: 'Which models of leadership are more likely to contribute to the improvement of PHEIs?' The research question seeks to contribute and expand upon existing research by identifying models of leadership and strategies that private HE leaders implement to guide improvement in their organisations. Being mindful of the evolving environment of HE and the Covid-19 pandemic, it is essential to explore the main features of the HE landscape that significantly impact on leadership in private HE sector and learn about the leaders' responses to these contextual factors, as well as the abilities and qualities that underpin good leadership in this sector.

The aim is to examine the practice of leadership within five outstanding PHEIs and identify an effective leadership model (s) that works best within these organisations. The study takes a qualitative approach in the form of case studies because it is ideal for investigating a contemporary phenomenon in depth and within its real-world setting, mainly when the case setting contains contextual conditions important for understanding the phenomenon (Fu et al., 2022). There will be five individual case studies relying on qualitative evidence through sources such as semi-structured interviews. The participants involved in this study include the three highest ranking leaders in a HE organisation such as: CEO (Chief Executive Officer), Principal, and Programme Coordinator. Multiple data collection methods will allow me to look into detailed interactions of the CEOs, Principals, and Programme Coordinators to gain an understanding of how these participants experienced leadership and how it impacted on their role, responsibilities, and sense of ownership of the improvement of their organisations.

The interest of the proposed research has been derived from my passion for education and experience as the current Chairman of Executive and the director of OBC (Oxford Business College), which is a PHEI with seven campuses in six of the England's most exciting cities including: London, Oxford, Nottingham, Slough, Coventry, and Birmingham.

Keywords: This paper contains a brief introduction, literature review, and the methodology.

I. INTRODUCTION

Leadership is the main ingredient for the success of organisations. Its context has been melded in Private Higher Education Institutions (PHEIs) by the shifts in technological modes of teaching and learning and its response to the demand of the new generation and competition. The purpose of this empirical study is to identify leadership practices and their effectiveness that will help PHEIs achieve institutional goals and vision, manage their operations, maintain good relationships, and lead with a high-quality education. The overarching question is: 'Which models of leadership are more likely to contribute to the improvement of PHEIs?' The research question seeks to contribute and expand upon existing research by identifying models of leadership and strategies that private HE leaders implement to guide improvement in their organisations. Being mindful of the evolving environment of HE and the Covid-19 pandemic, it is essential to explore the main features of the HE landscape that significantly impact on leadership in private HE sector and learn about the leaders' responses to these contextual factors, as well as the abilities and qualities that underpin good leadership in this sector.

The aim is to examine the practice of leadership within five outstanding PHEIs and identify an effective leadership model (s) that works best within these organisations. The study takes a qualitative approach in the form of case studies because it is ideal for investigating a contemporary phenomenon in depth and within its real-world setting, mainly when the case setting contains contextual conditions important for understanding the phenomenon (Fu et al., 2022). There will be five individual case studies relying on qualitative evidence through sources such as semi-structured interviews. The participants involved in this study include the three highest ranking leaders in a HE organisation such as: CEO (Chief Executive Officer), Principal, and Programme Coordinator. Multiple data collection methods will allow me to look into detailed interactions of the CEOs, Principals, and Programme Coordinators to gain an understanding of how these participants experienced leadership and how it impacted on their role, responsibilities, and sense of ownership of the improvement of their organisations.

The interest of the proposed research has been derived from my passion for education and experience as the current Chairman of Executive and

the director of OBC (Oxford Business College), which is a PHEI with seven campuses in six of the England's most exciting cities including: London, Oxford, Nottingham, Slough, Coventry, and Birmingham.

This paper contains a brief introduction, literature review, and the methodology.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Higher education is rapidly changing and leaders in PHEIs are faced with changing sets of challenges as they struggle with increasing competition, escalating cost and demand for improved quality (Watermeyer, Bolden, Knight, and Holm, 2022). Globalisation has also generated significant threat to local private institutions as many overseas universities have set up branch campuses within the country. Under such conditions, the leadership in private institutions has to exhibit considerable innovation and dynamism to confront the wide range of challenges facing them.

The purpose of this research study is to identify leadership practices and their effectiveness that will help PHE. It is observed that in the humanistic leadership theories period, leadership studies in higher education institutions are subjected to various leadership areas such as collaborative and distributed leadership (Youngs, 2017); transactional leadership (Sims *et al.*, 2021); responsible leadership (Akhtar *et al.*, 2020); instructional leadership (Shaked, 2021); transformational leadership (Sathiyaseelan, 2021); ethical leadership (Gok *et al.*, 2017) and servant leadership (Dahleez and Aboramadan, 2022). The issue of leadership in higher education institutions, especially whether different leadership styles exist in higher education institutions, whether they are necessary, and whether the same theory and application framework is valid for the higher education sector as in other institutions (Amzat and Idris, 2012; Siddique *et al.*, 2011) brought it to the fore. Because, as a large institution, a university is managed by various structures and administrative bodies therefore, leadership styles in higher education institutions refer to different management roles and titles, from strategic management to managerial roles, transformational and visionary roles (Settles *et al.*, 2019). In this way, it can be concluded that the roles of leaders in higher education can be complex and varied. This claim has particularly supported by Li *et al.* (2022) where emphasizing the complexity of the roles of education leaders in higher education, stating that they are responsible for fulfilling a variety of tasks from educational visionary to legal oversight. Apart from this, HE leaders are also responsible for the job satisfaction of lecturers, which is another important variable to increase the quality of education and training and to develop the educational performance at HEIs.

Suggesting a diverse form of leadership is required to enable PHEIs to survive and thrive in this ever-changing environment and set the way for future expansion. Hence, it is crucial to identify the skills of an individual who will lead, manage, and influence entire organisations and institutions, especially in changing situations (Korejan and Shahbazi, 2016).

The result of this study is the development of a leadership quality model for private HEIs. With the development of a leadership quality model for private HE, it is hoped that the quality of leadership in private HE will increase.

2.1 Research Questions

Overall research question:

Which models of leadership are more likely to contribute to the improvement of private Higher Education Institutions?

Sub-research Questions:

What are the main features of the Higher Education landscape (organisational, structural, social, ethical, political, etc) that impact on leadership within a private Higher Education institution?

What new or future leadership skills, competencies, and behaviours are required within a private Higher Education institution?

2.2 Aims and Objectives

Research indicates that there is a correlation between leadership style and school effectiveness (Leithwood and Jantzi, 2010; and Robinson, 2007). So, considering the important role of educational leaders in schools, colleges and universities, this research aims to find out the effective leadership model (s) that best contribute to the improvement of PHEIs in England.

To achieve the desired outcomes the following objectives are outlined:

Objectives

To explore the strategies used by HE leaders to initiate a change or sustain an improvement process within their organisations.

To learn about the main contextual factors that impact private HE leaders and their organisations.

To understand the leadership qualities that underpin good leadership within the current and future landscape of HE.

III. METHODOLOGY

I will be using a case study approach to investigate a phenomenon within its real-life context. As explained by Sharp (2009) case study research in education relates itself with people, places, and events by taking an interest in functioning of wholes rather than parts. The case in a case

study is usually a self-contained and coherent analysis with clear and well-defined boundaries in terms of participants, time, location, organisation and context or a combination of these (ibid. 2009).

The rationale is, firstly, case study approach provides rich and authentic data. Secondly, it is a descriptive and exploratory approach that is in line with my research questions. Finally, as Dawson (2009) asserts, case study research has a potential to provide the researcher with a level of detail which cannot be achieved by any other means because it involves: observing, describing, analysing and interpreting the behaviour of real people in real settings; exploring the characteristics and details of complex situations; and providing detailed and progressive stories (ibid.2009).

In terms of selection, I will use a purposeful sampling because the outstanding PHEIs are selected with specific qualities such as great leadership practices and leadership qualities that will help PHEIs achieve institutional goals and vision, manage their operations, maintain good relationships, and lead with a high-quality education

IV. RESEARCH METHOD

As mentioned earlier, the present study uses a case study approach relying on the qualitative evidence through sources such as semi-structured interviews. I use this method because this method will enable me to answer the main research questions outlined above.

To answer the main research question I will be using a case study approach to collect rich and authentic qualitative data in order to understand effective models of leadership that contribute to the improvement of PHEIs.

4.1 Participants

The participants involved in this study include the three highest ranking leaders from five outstanding private HE organisations such as: CEOs (Chief Executive Officers), Principals, and Programme Coordinators. Multiple data collection methods will allow me to look into detailed interactions of the CEOs, Principals, and Programme Coordinators to gain an understanding of how these participants experienced leadership and how it impacted on their role, responsibilities, and sense of ownership of the improvement of their organisations. Interviews will allow individuals to share their understanding regarding leadership and its value in higher education.

4.2 Data Analysis

I choose reflexive thematic analysis to analysis the qualitative data gathered through interviews. This approach as described by Braun and Clarke (2006) due to its suitability for understanding the complex narratives and subjective experiences of participants in this study. Reflexive thematic analysis is a method commonly used in qualitative research to identify and interpret patterns or themes within interview or textual data, while also considering the subjectivity and influence of the researcher on the analysis process (ibid. 2006). This approach enables me to delve into the meaning and experiences of the HE leaders, while also being aware of my own role in this research. By employing this method, the aim is to gain a deeper understanding of the intricacies and nuances of the practice of leadership in private HE.

4.3 Ethical Considerations

According to Gardner (2011) educational researchers should operate within an ethic of respect for any persons involved in the research they are undertaking. In this way individuals should be treated fairly, sensitively, with dignity, and within an ethic of respect and freedom from prejudice regardless of age, gender, sexuality, race, ethnicity, class, nationality, cultural identity, faith, disability, political belief or any other significant difference. This ethic of respect should apply to both the researchers and any individuals involved in the research either directly or indirectly.

Therefore, based on the ethic of respect, my responsibilities as a researcher include preparing voluntary informed consent (the condition in which participants understand and agree to their participation without any pressure, prior to the research getting underway); information outlining the purpose of the research, the types of data that will be collected and how the data will be used, reported and stored; openness and disclosure; right to withdraw; and privacy (the confidential and anonymous treatment of participants' data is considered necessary for the conduct of research) (ibid. 2011).

To fulfil the ethical requirements of this research all aspects of study will be conducted in accordance with the requirements of the University of West London (UWL) Research Project Ethics Committee.

Data collected during the research will be stored securely and safely and in accordance with UWL and schools' recommendations.

V. RESEARCH IMPACT

The main contribution of this research will be introducing an effective leadership model that assists private Higher Education institutions achieve institutional goals and vision, manage their operations, maintain good relationships, and lead with a high-quality education. Although there are many empirical studies in the literature about why leadership matters and the difference good leadership can make (Kiplangat *et al.*, 2017; Okan and Akyuz, 2015), but there is limited study about the factors and features that make it effective, particularly when the burdens of complexity weigh heavily. there is no study that clearly reveals the direction and effect of the relationship between leadership styles in HEIs

and academic staff's job satisfaction using the meta-analysis method (Watermeyer, Bolden, Knight, and Holm, 2022).

REFERENCE LIST

1. Akhtar, M. W., Karatepe, O. M., Syed, F., and Husnain, M. (2021) Leader knowledge hiding, feedback avoidance, and hotel employee outcomes: a moderated mediation model. *Int. J. Contemp. Hosp. Manag.* 34, 578–600. doi: 10.1108/IJCHM-04-2021-0545
2. Amzat, I. H., and Idris, D. A. R. (2012) Structural equation models of management and decision-making styles with job satisfaction of academic staff in Malaysian research university. *International Journal of Educational Management.* 26, 616–645. doi: 10.1108/095135412111263700
3. Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) Using thematic analysis in psychology, *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3 (2), 77-101. [Accessed December 2023]. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>
4. Dahleez, K., and Aboramadan, M. (2022) Servant leadership and job satisfaction in higher education: the mediating roles of organizational justice and organizational trust. *Int. J. Leadersh. Educ.*, 1–22. doi: 10.1080/13603124.2022.2052753
5. Dawson, C. (2009) *Introduction to Research Methods. A practical guide for anyone undertaking a research project.* 4th ed. United Kingdom: How to Books Ltd.
6. Fu, F., Wang, D., Li, W., Zhao, D., and Wu, Z. (2022) Overall fault diagnosability evaluation for dynamic systems: A quantitative–qualitative approach. *Automatica*, p. 146. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.automatica.2022.110591>
7. Gardner, J. (2011) Ethical guidelines for Educational Research. *Council of the British Educational Research Association.* [Viewed January 2024].
8. Gok, K., Sumanth, J. J., Bommer, W. H., Demirtas, O., Arslan, A., Eberhard, J., et al. (2017) You may not reap what you sow: How employees' moral awareness minimizes ethical leadership's positive impact on workplace deviance. *Journal of Business Ethics* 146:257–277. doi: 10.1007/s10551-017-3655-7
9. Kiplangat, H. K., Momanyi, M., and Kangethe, N. S. (2017) Dimensions of Kenyan university academic staff's job satisfaction in view of various managerial leadership practices. *J. Educ. Pract.* 8, pp: 120–129.
10. Korejan, M. M., and Shahbazi, H. (2016) An analysis of the transformational leadership theory. *Journal of fundamental and applied sciences*, 8(3), pp: 452-461.
11. Leithwood, K., Patten, S., and Jantzi, D. (2010) Testing a conception of how school leadership influences student learning. *Educational Administration Quarterly*, 46(5), 671–706.
12. Li, M., Yang, F., and Akhtar, M. W. (2022) Responsible leadership effect on career success: the role of work engagement and self-enhancement motives in education sector. *Front. Psychol.* 13, 1–9. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2022.888386
13. Okan, T., and Akyuz, A. M. (2015) Exploring the relationship between ethical leadership and job satisfaction with the mediating role of the level of loyalty to supervisor. *Bus. Econ. Res. J.* 6, 155–177.
14. Robinson, V. (2007) The Impact of Leadership on Student Outcomes: Making Sense of the Evidence. [Viewed December 2023]. http://research.acer.edu.au/research_conference_2007/5/
15. Settles, I. H., Brassel, S. T., Soranno, P. A., Cheruvellil, K. S., Montgomery, G. M., and Elliott, K. C. (2019) Team climate mediates the effect of diversity on environmental science team satisfaction and data sharing. *PLoS One* 14:e0219196. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0219196
16. Sathiyaseelan, S. (2021) Transformational leaders in higher education administration: understanding their profile through phenomenology. *Asia Pacific J. Educat.*, 1–16. doi: 10.1080/02188791.2021.1987185
17. Shaked, H. (2021) Instructional leadership in higher education: the case of Israel. *High. Educ. Q.* 75, 212–226. doi: 10.1111/hequ.12274
18. Sharp, J., (2009) *Success with your Education Research Project.* United Kingdom: Learning Mattered Ltd.
19. Siddique, A., Aslam, H. D., Khan, M., and Fatima, U. (2011) Impact of academic leadership on faculty's motivation and organizational effectiveness in higher education System. *International journal of academic research* 3, 3.730–3.737.
20. Sims, C., Carter, A., and Moore De Peralta, A. (2021) Do servant, transformational, transactional, and passive avoidant leadership styles influence mentoring competencies for faculty? A study of a gender equity leadership development program. *Hum. Resour. Dev. Q.* 32, 55–75. doi: 10.1002/hrdq.21408
21. Watermeyer, R., Bolden, R., Knight, C., and Holm, J. (2022) Leadership in global higher education, University of Bristol: CHET (Centre for Higher Education Transformations).
22. Youngs, H. (2017) A critical exploration of collaborative and distributed leadership in higher education: developing an alternative ontology through leadership-as-practice. *J. High. Educ. Policy Manag.* 39, 140–154. doi: 10.1080/1360080X.2017.1276662